

Factorial-Type Numerical Calender 2021

WELCOME - 2021
Mathematical Style

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Abstract

*This short work brings **factorial-type** numerical representations of the calender. It is based on a functional equation of three variables representing "day", "month" and "year". The results are based on 5! and 6!. First half of the year (January to June) is with 5!, and the second half of the year (July to December) is with 6!. It is given for the years ending in 21 and 2021. The the dates of other years can be calculated on similar lines.*

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3 Final Remarks

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1 Factorial-Type Numerical Representations of Year 21

Below are two ways of representing date and month of year 21 based on $5!$ and $6!$

Let's consider a function of two variable function

$$f(d, m) := 5! + d \times 10^4 + (m - 1) \times 10^2 + 10^0. \quad (1)$$

The number d and m represents the **day** and **month** respectively.

Based on (1) below are few examples:

Example 1.1. Let's suppose, we want to write *April 15, 21*, i.e., *15.04.21*. Let's consider $d = 15$ and $m = 04$ in (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(15, 04) &:= 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + (04 - 1) \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 150420, \text{ i.e., } 15.04.21 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.2. Let's suppose, we want to write *November 04, 21*, i.e., *04.11.21*. Let's consider $d = 04$ and $m = 11$ in (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(04, 11) &:= 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + (11 - 1) \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 5! + 4 \times 10^4 + 10 \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 041121, \text{ i.e., } 04.11.21. \end{aligned}$$

• Second Way

Let's consider the following function of two variables:

$$h(d, m) := 6! + d \times 10^4 + (m - 7) \times 10^2 + 10^0. \quad (2)$$

The number d and m represents the **days** and **months** respectively.

Based on (2) below are few examples:

Example 1.3. Let's suppose, we want to write *October 22, 21*, i.e., *22.10.21*. In this case, let's consider $d := 22$ and $m := 10$ in (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} h(22, 10) &:= 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + (10 - 7) \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 221020, \text{ i.e., } 22.10.21. \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.4. Let's suppose, we want to write *July 12, 21*, i.e., *12.07.21*. In this case, let's consider $d := 12$ and $m := 07$, in (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} h(12, 07) &:= 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + (07 - 7) \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 10^0 \\ &:= 120721, \text{ i.e., } 12.07.21. \end{aligned}$$

Above, we have seen two different functions given in (1) and (2). These two functions can be written together as a single function represented by the 5! and 6!. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} F(d, m) &:= 5! + d \times 10^4 + (m - 1) \times 10^2 + 10^0 \\ &:= 6! + d \times 10^4 + (m - 7) \times 10^2 + 10^0 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where **d** and **m** represents the **day** and **month** respectively.

Simplifying the above two functions, we get a single function given by

$$F(d, m) := d \times 10^4 + m \times 10^2 + 21. \tag{4}$$

The function given in (4) give the values in terms of powers of 10 with coefficients, while the expressions (1) and (2) are **factorial-type** representations. The expression (4) is always known in the literature, while the expressions (1) and (2) are new type studied by author [10] in 2020.

Below are few more examples given as remark of the expressions (1) and (2):

Remark 1.1. In all the three situations, below are some interesting examples:

$$\begin{aligned} f(01, 01) &:= 5! + 10^4 + 10^0 = 010121, \text{ i.e., } 01.01.21 \\ f(10, 10) &:= 5! + 10^5 + 10^0 = 100121, \text{ i.e., } 10.01.21 \\ h(01, 07) &:= 6! + 10^4 + 10^0 = 010721, \text{ i.e., } 01.07.21 \\ h(10, 07) &:= 6! + 10^5 + 10^0 = 100721, \text{ i.e., } 01.07.21 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1.2. From Remark 1.1, we observe that there is not very much difference either using 5! or 6!. While in case of year 20 [10], we use used 5!, 6! and 8! and the results were different in each case.

1.1 Month-Wise Numerical Representations

This section brings **month-wise** details of each day of year 21 by use of functions given in (1) and (2). The first six month, i.e., January to June are with 5! and the last six months, i.e., July to December are with 6!. Even though all the 12 months can be written with either 5! or 6!, but we preferred to divide it in two equal parts.

1.1.1 January-21

In the (1) consider $m = 1$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **January-21**.

◇ *January - 21* ◇

$$010121 := 5! + 01 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$020121 := 5! + 02 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$030121 := 5! + 03 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$040121 := 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$050121 := 5! + 05 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$060121 := 5! + 06 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$070121 := 5! + 07 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$080121 := 5! + 08 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$090121 := 5! + 09 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$100121 := 5! + 10 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$110121 := 5! + 11 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$120121 := 5! + 12 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$130121 := 5! + 13 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$140121 := 5! + 14 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$150121 := 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$160121 := 5! + 16 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$170121 := 5! + 17 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$180121 := 5! + 18 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$190121 := 5! + 19 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$200121 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$210121 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$220121 := 5! + 22 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$230121 := 5! + 23 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$240121 := 5! + 24 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$250121 := 5! + 25 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$260121 := 5! + 26 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$270121 := 5! + 27 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$280121 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$290121 := 5! + 29 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$300121 := 5! + 29 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$310121 := 5! + 31 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

1.1.2 February-21

In the (1) consider $m = 2$ and $d = 1$ to 28, then we have the following values representing the days of **February-21**.

◇ February - 21 ◇

$$010221 := 5! + 01 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020221 := 5! + 02 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030221 := 5! + 03 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040221 := 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050221 := 5! + 05 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060221 := 5! + 06 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070221 := 5! + 07 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080221 := 5! + 08 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090221 := 5! + 09 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100221 := 5! + 10 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110221 := 5! + 11 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120221 := 5! + 12 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130221 := 5! + 13 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140221 := 5! + 14 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150221 := 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160221 := 5! + 16 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170221 := 5! + 17 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180221 := 5! + 18 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190221 := 5! + 19 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200221 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210221 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220221 := 5! + 22 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230221 := 5! + 23 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240221 := 5! + 24 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250221 := 5! + 25 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260221 := 5! + 26 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270221 := 5! + 27 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280221 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.3 March-21

In the (1) consider $m = 3$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **March-21**.

◇ *March - 21* ◇

$$010321 := 5! + 01 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020321 := 5! + 02 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030321 := 5! + 03 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040321 := 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050321 := 5! + 05 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060321 := 5! + 06 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070321 := 5! + 07 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080321 := 5! + 08 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090321 := 5! + 09 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100321 := 5! + 10 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110321 := 5! + 11 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120321 := 5! + 12 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130321 := 5! + 13 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140321 := 5! + 14 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150321 := 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160321 := 5! + 16 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170321 := 5! + 17 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180321 := 5! + 18 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190321 := 5! + 19 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200321 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210321 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220321 := 5! + 22 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230321 := 5! + 23 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240321 := 5! + 24 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250321 := 5! + 25 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260321 := 5! + 26 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270321 := 5! + 27 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280321 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$290321 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$300321 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$310321 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.4 April-21

In the (1) consider $m = 4$ and $d = 1$ to 30, then we have the following values representing the days of **April-21**.

◇ April - 21 ◇

$$010421 := 5! + 01 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020421 := 5! + 02 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030421 := 5! + 03 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040421 := 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050421 := 5! + 05 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060421 := 5! + 06 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070421 := 5! + 07 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080421 := 5! + 08 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090421 := 5! + 09 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100421 := 5! + 10 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110421 := 5! + 11 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120421 := 5! + 12 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130421 := 5! + 13 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140421 := 5! + 14 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150421 := 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160421 := 5! + 16 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170421 := 5! + 17 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180421 := 5! + 18 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190421 := 5! + 19 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200421 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210421 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220421 := 5! + 22 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230421 := 5! + 23 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240421 := 5! + 24 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250421 := 5! + 25 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260421 := 5! + 26 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270421 := 5! + 27 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280421 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$290421 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$300421 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.5 May-21

In the (1) consider $5 = 3$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **May-21**.

◇ *May - 21* ◇

$$010521 := 5! + 01 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020521 := 5! + 02 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030521 := 5! + 03 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040521 := 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050521 := 5! + 05 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060521 := 5! + 06 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070521 := 5! + 07 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080521 := 5! + 08 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090521 := 5! + 09 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100521 := 5! + 10 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110521 := 5! + 11 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120521 := 5! + 12 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130521 := 5! + 13 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140521 := 5! + 14 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150521 := 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160521 := 5! + 16 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170521 := 5! + 17 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180521 := 5! + 18 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190521 := 5! + 19 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200521 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210521 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220521 := 5! + 22 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230521 := 5! + 23 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240521 := 5! + 24 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250521 := 5! + 25 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260521 := 5! + 26 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270521 := 5! + 27 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280521 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$290521 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$300521 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$310521 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.6 June-21

In the (1) consider $m = 6$ and $d = 1$ to 30, then we have the following values representing the days of **June-21**.

◇ June - 21 ◇

$$010621 := 5! + 01 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020621 := 5! + 02 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030621 := 5! + 03 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040621 := 5! + 04 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050621 := 5! + 05 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060621 := 5! + 06 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070621 := 5! + 07 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080621 := 5! + 08 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090621 := 5! + 09 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100621 := 5! + 10 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110621 := 5! + 11 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120621 := 5! + 12 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130621 := 5! + 13 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140621 := 5! + 14 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150621 := 5! + 15 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160621 := 5! + 16 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170621 := 5! + 17 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180621 := 5! + 18 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190621 := 5! + 19 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200621 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210621 := 5! + 21 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220621 := 5! + 22 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230621 := 5! + 23 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240621 := 5! + 24 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250621 := 5! + 25 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260621 := 5! + 26 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270621 := 5! + 27 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280621 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$290621 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$300621 := 5! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.7 July-21

In the (2) consider $m = 7$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **July-21**.

◇ July - 21 ◇

$$010721 := 6! + 01 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$020721 := 6! + 02 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$030721 := 6! + 03 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$040721 := 6! + 04 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$050721 := 6! + 05 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$060721 := 6! + 06 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$070721 := 6! + 07 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$080721 := 6! + 08 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$090721 := 6! + 09 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$100721 := 6! + 10 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$110721 := 6! + 11 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$120721 := 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$130721 := 6! + 13 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$140721 := 6! + 14 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$150721 := 6! + 15 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$160721 := 6! + 16 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$170721 := 6! + 17 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$180721 := 6! + 18 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$190721 := 6! + 19 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$200721 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$210721 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$220721 := 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$230721 := 6! + 23 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$240721 := 6! + 24 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$250721 := 6! + 25 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$260721 := 6! + 26 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$270721 := 6! + 27 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$280721 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$290721 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$300721 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

$$310721 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^0$$

1.1.8 August-21

In the (2) consider $m = 8$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **August-21**.

◇ August - 21 ◇

$$010821 := 6! + 01 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020821 := 6! + 02 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030821 := 6! + 03 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040821 := 6! + 04 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050821 := 6! + 05 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060821 := 6! + 06 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070821 := 6! + 07 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080821 := 6! + 08 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090821 := 6! + 09 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100821 := 6! + 10 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110821 := 6! + 11 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120821 := 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130821 := 6! + 13 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140821 := 6! + 14 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150821 := 6! + 15 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160821 := 6! + 16 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170821 := 6! + 17 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180821 := 6! + 18 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190821 := 6! + 19 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200821 := 6! + 20 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210821 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220821 := 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230821 := 6! + 23 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240821 := 6! + 24 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250821 := 6! + 25 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260821 := 6! + 26 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270821 := 6! + 27 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280821 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$290821 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$300821 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$310821 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.9 September-21

In the (2) consider $m = 9$ and $d = 1$ to 30, then we have the following values representing the days of **September-21**.

◇ *September - 21* ◇

$$010921 := 6! + 01 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$020921 := 6! + 02 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$030921 := 6! + 03 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$040921 := 6! + 04 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$050921 := 6! + 05 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$060921 := 6! + 06 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$070921 := 6! + 07 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$080921 := 6! + 08 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$090921 := 6! + 09 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$100921 := 6! + 10 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$110921 := 6! + 11 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$120921 := 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$130921 := 6! + 13 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$140921 := 6! + 14 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$150921 := 6! + 15 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$160921 := 6! + 16 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$170921 := 6! + 17 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$180921 := 6! + 18 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$190921 := 6! + 19 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$200921 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$210921 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$220921 := 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$230921 := 6! + 23 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$240921 := 6! + 24 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$250921 := 6! + 25 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$260921 := 6! + 26 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$270921 := 6! + 27 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$280921 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$290921 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$300921 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.10 October-21

In the (2) consider $m = 10$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **October-21**.

◇ *October - 21* ◇

$$011021 := 6! + 01 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$021021 := 6! + 02 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$031021 := 6! + 03 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$041021 := 6! + 04 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$051021 := 6! + 05 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$061021 := 6! + 06 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$071021 := 6! + 07 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$081021 := 6! + 08 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$091021 := 6! + 09 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$101021 := 6! + 10 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$111021 := 6! + 11 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$121021 := 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$131021 := 6! + 13 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$141021 := 6! + 14 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$151021 := 6! + 15 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$161021 := 6! + 16 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$171021 := 6! + 17 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$181021 := 6! + 18 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$191021 := 6! + 19 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$201021 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$211021 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$221021 := 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$231021 := 6! + 23 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$241021 := 6! + 24 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$251021 := 6! + 25 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$261021 := 6! + 26 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$271021 := 6! + 27 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$281021 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$291021 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$301021 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$311021 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 3 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.11 November-21

In the (2) consider $m = 11$ and $d = 1$ to 30, then we have the following values representing the days of **November-21**.

◇ *November - 21* ◇

$$011121 := 6! + 01 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$021121 := 6! + 02 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$031121 := 6! + 03 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$041121 := 6! + 04 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$051121 := 6! + 05 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$061121 := 6! + 06 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$071121 := 6! + 07 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$081121 := 6! + 08 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$091121 := 6! + 09 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$101121 := 6! + 10 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$111121 := 6! + 11 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$121121 := 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$131121 := 6! + 13 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$141121 := 6! + 14 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$151121 := 6! + 15 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$161121 := 6! + 16 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$171121 := 6! + 17 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$181121 := 6! + 18 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$191121 := 6! + 19 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$201121 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$211121 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$221121 := 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$231121 := 6! + 23 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$241121 := 6! + 24 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$251121 := 6! + 25 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$261121 := 6! + 26 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$271121 := 6! + 27 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$281121 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$291121 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$301121 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 4 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

1.1.12 December-21

In the (2) consider $m = 12$ and $d = 1$ to 31, then we have the following values representing the days of **December-21**.

◇ *December - 21* ◇

$$011221 := 6! + 01 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$161221 := 6! + 16 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$021221 := 6! + 02 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$171221 := 6! + 17 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$031221 := 6! + 03 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$181221 := 6! + 18 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$041221 := 6! + 04 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$191221 := 6! + 19 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$051221 := 6! + 05 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$201221 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$061221 := 6! + 06 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$211221 := 6! + 21 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$071221 := 6! + 07 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$221221 := 6! + 22 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$081221 := 6! + 08 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$231221 := 6! + 23 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$091221 := 6! + 09 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$241221 := 6! + 24 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$101221 := 6! + 10 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$251221 := 6! + 25 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$111221 := 6! + 11 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$261221 := 6! + 26 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$121221 := 6! + 12 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$271221 := 6! + 27 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$131221 := 6! + 13 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$281221 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$141221 := 6! + 14 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$291221 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$151221 := 6! + 15 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$301221 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

$$311221 := 6! + 28 \times 10^4 + 5 \times 10^2 + 10^0$$

2 Year-Wise Numerical Representations

The previous section give the results and functions only for the year ending in 20 instead of 2021. This section brings representations in terms of **day**, **month** and **year**. See below two general functions based on the 5! and 6!. Below are some examples of functions written with 5!, and 6!, with variables for **day**, **month** and **year**.

Let's consider the following three functions:

$$F(d, m, x) := 5! \times 10^2 + d \times 10^6 + (m - 1) \times 10^4 + x \quad (5)$$

$$H(d, m, x) := 6! \times 10^2 + d \times 10^6 + (m - 7) \times 10^4 + x \quad (6)$$

where **d**, **m** and **y** with **y=2000+x** represents the **day**, **month** and **year** respectively.

Simplifying the above three functions, we get a single function:

$$K(d, m, y) = d \times 10^6 + m \times 10^4 + y \quad (7)$$

where **d**, **m** and **y** represents the **day**, **month** and **year** respectively.

Remark 2.1. The function (7) is in terms of **powers of 10**, while the functions (5) and (6) are **factorial-type** representations. The function (7) is always known in the literature, while the functions (5) and (6) are new in the literature. These are studied by author in [10].

Below are some examples of the functions (5) and (6).

Example 2.1. Let's suppose, we want to write **March 18, 2021**, i.e., **18.03.2021**. In this case, $d = 18$, $m = 03$ and $x = 2021 - 2000 = 21$. According to (5) and (6), we have

$$F(18, 03, 20) := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + (03 - 1) \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$H(18, 03, 20) := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + (03 - 7) \times 10^4 + 21$$

After simplifications, we have

$$F(18, 03, 21) := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21 = 18032021, \text{ i.e., } 18.03.2021$$

$$H(18, 03, 21) := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 - 4 \times 10^4 + 21 = 18032021, \text{ i.e., } 18.03.2021$$

Equivalently, as a power of 10, we have

$$18032021 := 18 \times 10^6 + 03 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^3 + 21.$$

Example 2.2. Let's suppose, we want to write **December 03, 2023**, i.e., **03.12.2023**. In this case, $d = 03$, $m = 12$ and $x = 2023 - 2000 = 23$. According to (5) and (6), we have

$$F(03, 12, 23) := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + (12 - 1) \times 10^4 + 23$$

$$H(03, 12, 23) := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + (12 - 7) \times 10^4 + 23$$

After simplifications, we have

$$F(03, 12, 23) := 5! \times 10^2 + 3 \times 10^6 + 11 \times 10^4 + 23 = 03122023, \text{ i.e., } 03.12.2023$$

$$H(03, 12, 23) := 6! \times 10^2 + 3 \times 10^6 + 05 \times 10^4 + 23 = 03122023, \text{ i.e., } 03.12.2023$$

Equivalently, as a power of 10, we have

$$03122023 := 03 \times 10^6 + 12 \times 10^4 + 2 \times 10^3 + 23.$$

Example 2.3. Let's suppose, we want to write *September 9, 2999*, i.e., *09.09.2999*. In this case, $d = 09$, $m = 09$ and $x = 2999 - 2000 = 999$. According to (5) and (6), we have

$$F(09, 09, 999) := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + (09 - 1) \times 10^4 + 999$$

$$H(09, 09, 999) := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + (09 - 7) \times 10^4 + 999$$

After simplifications, we have

$$F(09, 09, 999) := 5! \times 10^2 + 9 \times 10^6 + 8 \times 10^4 + 999 = 09092999, \text{ i.e., } 09.09.2999$$

$$H(09, 09, 999) := 6! \times 10^2 + 9 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 999 = 09092999, \text{ i.e., } 09.09.2999$$

The above two Examples 2.2 and 2.3 are for the years bigger than or equal to 2000, where year is represented by $y = x + 2000$. In order to write example for the year less than 2000, we shall use the same definition of y , i.e., $y = x + 2000$. See below some examples.

Example 2.4. Let's suppose, we want to write *November 11, 1234*, i.e., *11.11.1234*. In this case, $d = 11$, $m = 11$ and $x = 1234 - 2000 = -766$. According to (5) and (6), we have

$$F(11, 11, -766) := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + (11 - 1) \times 10^4 - 766$$

$$H(11, 11, -766) := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + (11 - 7) \times 10^4 - 766$$

After simplifications, we have

$$F(11, 11, -766) := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 10 \times 10^4 - 766 = 11111234, \text{ i.e., } 11.11.1234$$

$$H(11, 11, -766) := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 04 \times 10^4 - 766 = 11111234, \text{ i.e., } 11.11.1234$$

Example 2.5. Let's suppose, we want to write *September 03, 688*, i.e., *03.09.688*. In this case, $d = 03$, $m = 09$ and $x = 688 - 2000 = -1312$. According to (5) and (6), we have

$$F(03, 09, -1312) := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + (09 - 1) \times 10^4 - 1312$$

$$H(03, 09, -1312) := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + (09 - 7) \times 10^4 - 1312$$

After simplifications, we have

$$F(03, 09, -1312) := 5! \times 10^2 + 3 \times 10^6 + 8 \times 10^4 - 1312 = 03090688, \text{ i.e., } 03.09.0688$$

$$H(03, 09, -1312) := 6! \times 10^2 + 3 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 - 1312 = 03090688, \text{ i.e., } 03.09.0688$$

Remark 2.2. Analysing the Examples 2.1-2.5, we observe that the functions given in (5) and (6) are valid for any year independent of bigger or less than 2000.

The subsection below give the **month-wise** details for the year 2021.

2.1 Month-Wise Representations of 2021

2.1.1 January-2021

In expression (5), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 1$ and $x = 21$, we get the following numerical representations for the month **January-2021**.

◇ *January - 2021* ◇

$$01012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$02012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$03012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$04012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$05012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$06012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$07012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$08012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$09012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$10012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$11012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$12012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$13012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$14012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$15012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$16012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$17012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$18012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$19012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$20012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$21012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$22012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$23012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$24012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$25012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$26012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$27012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$28012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$29012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$30012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$31012021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 21$$

2.1.2 February-2021

In expression (5), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 28$, $m = 2$ and $x = 21$, we get the following numerical representations for the month **February-2021**.

◇ *February - 2021* ◇

$$01022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$02022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$03022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$04022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$05022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$06022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$07022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$08022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$09022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$10022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$11022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$12022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$13022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$14022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$15022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$16022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$17022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$18022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$19022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$20022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$21022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$22022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$23022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$24022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$25022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$26022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$27022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$28022021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.3 March-2021

In expression (5), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 3$ and $x = 21$, we get the following representations for the month **March-2021**.

◇ *March - 2021* ◇

$$01032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$02032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$03032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$04032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$05032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$06032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$07032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$08032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$09032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$10032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$11032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$12032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$13032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$14032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$15032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$16032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$17032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$18032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$19032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$20032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$21032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$22032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$23032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$24032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$25032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$26032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$27032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$28032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$29032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$30032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$31032021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.4 April-2021

In expression (5), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 30$, $m = 4$ and $x = 21$, we get the following representations for the month **April-2021**.

◇ April - 2021 ◇

$$01042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$02042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$03042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$04042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$05042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$06042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$07042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$08042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$09042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$10042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$11042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$12042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$13042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$14042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$15042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$16042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$17042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$18042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$19042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$20042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$21042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$22042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$23042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$24042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$25042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$26042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$27042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$28042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$29042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$30042021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.5 May-2021

In expression (5), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 5$ and $x = 21$, we get the following representations for the month **May-2021**.

◇ *May - 2021* ◇

$$01052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$02052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$03052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$04052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$05052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$06052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$07052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$08052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$09052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$10052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$11052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$12052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$13052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$14052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$15052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$16052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$17052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$18052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$19052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$20052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$21052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$22052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$23052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$24052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$25052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$26052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$27052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$28052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$29052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$30052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$31052021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.6 June-2021

In expression (5), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 30$, $m = 6$ and $x = 21$, we get the following representations for the month **June-2021**.

◇ June - 2021 ◇

$01062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$16062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$02062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$17062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$03062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$18062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$04062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$19062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$05062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$20062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$06062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$21062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$07062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$22062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$08062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$23062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$09062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$24062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$10062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$25062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$11062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$26062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$12062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$27062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$13062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$28062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$14062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$29062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$
$15062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$	$30062021 := 5! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$

2.1.7 July-2021

In expression (6), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 7$ and $x = 21$ we get the following representations for the month **July-2021**.

◇ July - 2021 ◇

$$01072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$02072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$03072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$04072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$05072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$06072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$07072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$08072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$09072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$10072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$11072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$12072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$13072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$14072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$15072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$16072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$17072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$18072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$19072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$20072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$21072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$22072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$23072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$24072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$25072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$26072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$27072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$28072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$29072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$30072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 21$$

$$31072021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 21$$

2.1.8 August-2021

In expression (6), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 8$ and $x = 21$ we get the following representations for the month **August-2021**.

◇ August - 2021 ◇

$$01082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$02082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$03082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$04082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$05082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$06082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$07082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$08082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$09082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$10082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$11082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$12082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$13082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$14082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$15082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$16082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$17082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$18082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$19082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$20082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$21082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$22082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$23082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$24082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$25082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$26082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$27082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$28082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$29082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$30082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$31082021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.9 September-2021

In expression (6), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 30$, $m = 9$ and $x = 21$ we get the following representations for the month **September-2021**.

◇ *September - 2021* ◇

$01092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$16092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$02092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$17092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$03092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$18092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$04092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$19092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$05092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$20092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$06092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$21092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$07092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$22092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$08092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$23092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$09092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$24092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$10092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$25092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$11092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$26092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$12092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$27092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$13092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$28092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$14092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$29092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$
$15092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$	$30092021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 21$

2.1.10 October-2021

In expression (6), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 10$ and $x = 21$ we get the following representations for the month **October-2021**.

◇ *October - 2021* ◇

$$01102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$02102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$03102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$04102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$05102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$06102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$07102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$08102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$09102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$10102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$11102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$12102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$13102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$14102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$15102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$16102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$17102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$18102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$19102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$20102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$21102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$22102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$23102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$24102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$25102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$26102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$27102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$28102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$29102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$30102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$31102021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 3 \times 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.11 November-2021

In expression (6), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 30$, $m = 11$ and $x = 21$ we get the following representations for the month **November-2021**.

◇ *November - 2021* ◇

$$01112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$16112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$02112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$17112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$03112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$18112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$04112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$19112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$05112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$20112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$06112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$21112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$07112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$22112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$08112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$23112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$09112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$24112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$10112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$25112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$11112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$26112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$12112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$27112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$13112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$28112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$14112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$29112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$15112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$30112021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 21$$

2.1.12 December-2021

In expression (6), let's consider $d = 1$ to $d = 31$, $m = 11$ and $x = 21$ we get the following representations for the month **December-2021**.

◇ *December - 2021* ◇

$$01122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 01 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$02122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$03122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 03 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$04122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 04 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$05122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 05 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$06122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 06 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$07122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$08122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 08 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$09122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 09 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$10122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$11122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 11 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$12122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$13122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 13 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$14122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 14 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$15122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 15 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$16122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 16 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$17122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 17 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$18122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 18 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$19122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 19 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$20122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$21122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 21 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$22122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$23122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 23 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$24122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 24 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$25122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 25 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$26122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 26 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$27122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 27 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$28122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 28 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$29122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 29 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$30122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 30 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

$$31122021 := 6! \times 10^2 + 31 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 + 21$$

3 Final Remarks

- (i) From the Examples 2.2 to 2.5, we observe that writing the years apart from 2021, we have same kind of results using any of two factorials, i.e., 5! or 6!. Let's see below few more examples with 5! and 6!.

$$10.05.2601 := 10052601 = 5! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 + 4 \times 10^4 + 601$$

$$10.05.2601 := 10052601 = 6! \times 10^2 + 10 \times 10^6 - 2 \times 10^4 + 601$$

$$12.03.2888 := 12032888 = 5! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 + 2 \times 10^4 + 888$$

$$12.03.2888 := 12032888 := 6! \times 10^2 + 12 \times 10^6 - 4 \times 10^4 + 888$$

$$07.06.1246 := 07061246 = 5! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 + 5 \times 10^4 - 754$$

$$07.06.1246 := 07061246 = 6! \times 10^2 + 07 \times 10^6 - 1 \times 10^4 - 754$$

$$22.11.0889 := 22110889 = 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 10 \times 10^4 - 1111$$

$$22.11.0889 := 22110889 = 6! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 04 \times 10^4 - 1111$$

- (ii) The days **02.02.2021**, **20.02.2021** and **22.02.2021** are two digits day happened **February, 2021**. The first one is **palindromic**. It can be seen in a **palindromic magic square** appeared in Alex Bellos's [14] column "**The Guardian**". For more study on these numbers related with magic squares, see author's work [9]. Even though, these numbers appeared in a table of **February-2021**, let's see them again

$$02.02.2021 := 02022021 = 5! \times 10^2 + 02 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$20.02.2021 := 02022021 = 5! \times 10^2 + 20 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

$$22.02.2021 := 02022021 = 5! \times 10^2 + 22 \times 10^6 + 10^4 + 21$$

- (iii) A different kind of work connected with numbers and magic squares connected by dates is done by author [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. One of these work transformed in a **stamp** published by **Macau Post Office, China** [16]. This also appeared in Alex Bellos's column [15] "**The Guardian**". Also appeared in Wikipedia [17].
- (iv) There are two references [7, 8] summarizing author's work on numbers for the years 2019 and 2020. The year 2019 appeared in a **YouTube** by Matt Parker [11]. The year 2020 appeared in Alex Bellos's [12, 13] column "**The Guardian**". These references are also given. Author's more study on numbers and Magic Squares can be seen in **Web-site**: <https://inderjtaneja.com>.
- (v) This work brings the **Calender** using the two types factorials, i.e., 5! and 6!. First half of the year (January to June) is with 5!, and the second half (July to December) is with 6!.

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